
TOURISM PRODUCTS' DIMENSIONS AND SATISFACTION OF TOURISTS' NEEDS AMONG TOURISM SITES IN SOUTH EAST, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The aim of the study was to investigate the influence of tourism products' dimensions on satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria. Specific objectives were to: examine the influence of destination sites attraction and destination price on satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria. A survey research design was used for the study. 41 was total sites in South East, Nigeria. Sample size of study was three hundred and eighty four (384) and convenience sampling technique was adopted for selecting the respondents that completed the questionnaire. After data analysis, it was found that destination sites attraction and destination price had no significant positive influence on satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria. In the light of the findings, it was concluded that tourism products' dimensions had no significant positive influence on satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria. Therefore, it was recommended that government should improve on destination sites' attractiveness, facility, image, accessibility in order to make prices affordable to tourists who visit Nigeria as well as improve tourism revenue in Nigeria.

Keywords: *Tourism Products' Dimensions, Satisfaction, destination sites attraction, destination price and satisfaction of tourists' needs.*

INTRODUCTION

During the pre-historic stage of man's economic development, there was no organized production of any kind and so man depended on nature's provision for survival. At this stage, man moved from place to place to hunt for games and search for agricultural products grown by nature. However, tourism business can be traced to the era of transportation revolution which occurred in the nineteenth century or at barter stage of man's economic development. At barter stage, individuals had to travel long distances to exchange what they produced for what they do not have. Early travel was done by means of human portorage, beast of burden, canoes and carts. Later on other and better means of travel were developed such as vehicles, train, boat, and aircraft. It should be noted that early travel was undertaken mainly for the purposes of food, trade, waging wars, conquering new lands and for religious reasons (Ogili, Olewe & Eneh, 2023).

Nowadays, more than ever before, people travel within and outside the country of their origin not only for trading but also for medical treatments, marriages, academic and religious conferences, leisure, relaxations, holidays, sightseeing and enjoyment. These fuelled the need for the development and marketing of tourism products. The world over, tourism is recognized as the world’s largest industry. It accounts for about 7% of world capital investment with revenue predicted to rise up to 5.980 billion dollars by the year 2031 (Ogili, Olewe & Eneh, 2023).

Table 1.1 below shows international tourists’ arrivals in different continents of the world in 2020.

Region	International Tourist Arrivals	International Tourist Receipts (US)
Europe	548 million (51%)	\$ 509 billion (41%)
Asia pacific	263 million (23%)	\$ 377 billion (30%)
Americas	182 million (16%)	\$ 274 billion (22%)
Africa	56 million (5%)	\$ 39 billion (4%)
Middle East	50 million (4%)	\$ 36 billion (3%)

Source: UNWTO, 2020

Table 1.1 above shows global tourists’ visitation trends in different regions of the world with Europe accounting for the highest (41%) tourism receipts, followed by Asia pacific (30%), Americas (22%), Africa (4%) and Middle East (3%). The implication is that Africa tourism receipt is very poor even when the continent has good natural heritage. It is in recognition of this fact that the World Trade Organization (WTO, 2020) noted that tourism and hospitality industry is one of the greatest industries in Africa but most under invested assets, with market receipt worth \$36 billion (4%) but has \$203.7 billion of untapped potential which represents four times its current level (Ogili, Olewe & Eneh, 2023).

Similarly, Nigeria’s tourism receipt situation is not much different from that of Africa. Nigeria’s tourism landscape is extremely rich and beautiful for global tourist attraction. The weather, climate, vegetation, quality airspace, sunshine, beautiful scenery, the rocks, waterfalls, captivating beaches, historical relics, rich cultural diversity, parks, game reserves, ancient caves, captivating shopping malls, social and religious attractions, friendly people and wildlife are Nigeria’s tourism assets. Nigeria’s tourism market potential is huge, even though the receipt is quite small (Ejionueme & Nebo, 2021).

Customer satisfaction is one of the greatest tools in steering the growth of the tourism industry (Forozia, *et al*, 2018). In most cases, before a tourist visits a destination, he forms a set of expectations based on previous experience, press reports, advertising, common belief or what people say about the place. Evidence from the review of related empirical studies would support the conclusion that despite the quantum of studies in tourism particularly in the mainstream literature; significant knowledge-gap still exist with regards to determination of product dimensions that are likely to produce tourists’ satisfaction among tourism sites particularly in South-East, Nigerian context. Based on this gap in knowledge, the aim of this research was to determine the influence of tourism products’ dimensions on satisfaction of tourists’ needs among tourism sites in South-East, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

With the disappointing economic performance and the rating of Nigeria as the 103rd poorest nation in the world, calls have been made on both private and public sectors for diversified means of improving Nigeria's economic performance rather than heavy reliance on one-product (oil) export portfolio. These calls have continued to receive a heightened attention based on scholarly advocacy that diversified investments, particularly into the non-oil investment remains a viable and feasible option for Nigeria's hope for sustainable economic development in the 21st century (Anyanwu & Nkamnebe, 2013).

Excessive reliance on crude petroleum products has been pointed out as the major source of Nigeria's backwardness in economic development as evidenced in its high unemployment, inflation, insecurity, crime and poverty and illiteracy rates. The country also has a disappointing performance in other economic development parameters specifically in its GDP, GNI, Per capital income, Naira value, life expectancy rate and foreign exchange earnings. Nigeria's budgets for education, agriculture, transportation, information and communication, aviation, security and others all depend heavily on expectation from oil proceeds which signals a high danger for a country that take her economic development seriously. Experts in economic development have suggested that diversified investment is a sure way to improve Nigeria's economic development. This researcher try to close this gap in knowledge by ascertaining the extent to which tourism products' dimensions influence tourists' satisfaction among tourism sites in South-East, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study was to examine the influence of tourism products' dimensions on satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria. Specific objectives include to;

- i. Examine the extent influence of destination attraction on the satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria.
- ii. Determine the extent influence of destination price on the satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Tourism

Emeji, Odey and Bullus (2016), cited the definition of tourism from the International Association of Scientific Experts in Tourism (IASSET) as the sum of the phenomenon and relationship arising from the travel and stay of nonresidents, in so far as they do not lead to permanent residence. The term, tourism has been variously defined. For Gilbert (1990), tourism is a form of recreation which involves travel to a less familiar destination or community for a short-term period, in order to satisfy a consumer's need for one or a combination of activities.

Destination Attraction

These are attractive places tourist visit for pleasure, sightseeing and interest when they arrive in a destination. An attraction refers to a place or anything that appeals to tourists to visit any destination (Suanmali, 2021). Tourist attractions include natural attractions, cultural attractions, and recreation and activities. Lascu *et al.* (2018) described attractions as the determinant of the destination image that affects tourist satisfaction. These attractions include: natural attractions such as mountains and valleys, scenery and natural attractions, gardens and springs, drive, parks, lakes, rivers, wildlife, caves, and underground formations.

Destination Price

Price is the amount of money charged for a good or service whereas pricing is the act or process of deterring the price of a product. Pricing by its nature is one of the most delicate elements of the marketing mix or functions. Delicate in the sense that wrong pricing can lead to business failure. From the buyers' perspective, the price of a product means the value.

Satisfaction of Tourists' Needs

Tourist satisfaction has attracted the attention of several authors who have defined it in different ways. Philip and Hazlett (2017) tourist satisfaction occurs when the tourist's perception that his or her expectations have been met or surpassed. If the product or service performance falls short of expectation, the tourist is said to be dissatisfied. If performance matches expectations, the tourist is said to be satisfied. If the performance exceeds expectations, the tourist is highly satisfied or delighted (Philip & Hazlett, 2017).

Theoretical Framework

Mehradian-Russel Stimulus-Response Theory

This theory holds that "feelings determine how people will respond to environment. It states that the conscious and unconscious perception and interpretation of the environment influence how people feel. People's feelings in turn determine their responses to that environment.

Figure 1: Mehrabian-Russel Stimulus-Response Model

The above model shows that environmental stimuli which in this study are attraction sites, destination facilities and accessibility to the destinations all can affect tourists' feelings or mood. Consumer mood state or feelings are expressed in various forms such as happiness, pleasure, confidence, joy, excitement, anger, frustration, anxiety, fear, depression, shame, guilt etc. consumer feelings will determine response behaviour to the environment which may be approach or avoidance. Approach behaviour means that the customer feels good about the environment and this will result in business patronage while avoidance means that the customer dislikes the environment and may likely depart without buying anything.

The implication of this theory to tourism marketing is that managers of these firms should ensure that the physical environment elements such as interior decorations, exterior facilities, and employee's corporate identity are designed to trigger favourable consumer feelings or mood states. Good feelings are likely to produce favourable purchase response (approach) (Ejionueme & Nebo, 2021).

The implications of this theory to the current study is that tourism products dimensions such as destination environment which may include such things as natural attractions (e.g ocean beaches, waster falls, caves and mountains), man-made attraction (monuments, parks, garden, shopping malls, zoo, ranches, game reserve, international stadium, airports and five star hotels) socio-cultural attractions (museums, customer, food-ways, special events, festivals, marriages and social engagements) and religious attractions (natural churches, prayers camps and religious conferences), network of roads, destination price, destination images, security and accommodations create either favourable or unfavorable emotions (feelings) which in turn determine satisfaction or dissatisfaction.

Empirical Review

Biswas, Omar and Rashid-Radha (2020) examined the impact of tourist attractions and accessibility on tourists' satisfaction: the moderating role of tourists' age. The outcomes got from Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) using the SmartPLS v3 uncovered that age significantly moderated the relationship between attraction and tourist satisfaction as well as accessibility and tourist satisfaction.

Nyoman, Akhmad and Baiq (2021) studied the effect of tourist attractiveness on tourist satisfaction and revisit intention in the pandemic period in Indonesian. The tourism sector is one of the mainstays of local revenue. Gili Trawangan is one of several beautiful panoramic views in West Nusa Tenggara. This research aims to prove the influence of tourist attractiveness on tourist satisfaction and revisit intentions. The result showed that Tourist Attractiveness has a positive and significant influence on Tourist Satisfaction and Revisit Intentions.

Anibal, N'dami, Bambang and Sina (2023) examined enhancing tourist loyalty through destination attributes and the mediating role of tourist satisfaction in Nigeria. This study examines the effect of destination attributes on tourist satisfaction in Gili Trawangan (Lombok), West Nusa Tenggara. Furthermore, our research also analyzes the impact on tourist loyalty. The research sample focuses on tourists who have visited Gili Trawangan (Lombok) two times or more. Our findings show a positive correlation between destination attributes and the number of tourists.

Engelina and Melville (2021) confirmed factors influencing pricing in the accommodation sector in South Africa. Price is a significant factor of competitiveness. Price is a complex issue and is determined by a variety of demand and supply factors. These resulted in ten factors, namely environmental qualities, amenities, image, management factor, positioning, quality service factor, infrastructure service factor, location, marketing and product quality factor. The results revealed that the major factors in pricing are service quality, image and product quality.

Mariyanti, Husin, Wijaya, Sari, Putri, Abdilla and Putra (2023) examined the effect of perceived price fairness on revisit intention of local guest's sharia hotel: customer satisfaction as mediation in Ghana.

This paper aims to investigate the effect of perceived price fairness on the revisit intention of Sharia hotel guests in Padang City, as well as the mediating role of perceived customer satisfaction in the relationship between Perceived Price Fairness and Revisit Intention. The results show that perceived price fairness dramatically influences the level of customer satisfaction for Syariah hotel guests.

Gaps in Empirical Review

Geographical area: Previous studies on this area were done in other geographical areas other than South-Eastern part of Nigeria. **Variable studied:** Past similar studies were done using few product-related variables. However this study differs from others by exploring five major tourism product dimensions which include: destination attraction sites, destination prices. These five tourism product dimensions were not given considerable attention by past scholar on this subject.

METHODOLOGY

A survey design was the specific design that the researcher employed. The advantage of this design is that data can be collected less expensively and within a short time. Primary data refer to original data collected basically for the purpose of the study. Primary sources of data were used in this study by means of structured questionnaire. A total of 41 attraction sites exist in the South-Eastern State of Nigeria. As a result, the population of study comprised all the actual visitors aged 18 years and older who had visited any of the 41 attraction sites located in South-Eastern Nigeria in the last five years from their book records. The census of the actual visitors to these attraction sites was not available, therefore, the population of the study is deemed unknown or infinite while sample size was 384 with help of Topman's formula. Convenience sampling technique was adopted for selecting the respondents that completed the questionnaire since sampling frame was not available. Structured questionnaire was adopted for the collection of data from tourists' who had visited any of the attraction sites in the five South-Eastern States, Nigeria. The analyses of data were subjected to simple statistical treatment to be organized and presented in tables and percentages. The questionnaire responses were grouped into various categories and entered in the SPSS version 20 software to facilitate analysis using descriptive statistics. Frequency distribution tables were introduced to summarize the data from the respondents. The data expressed in scale. Data were presented in tables, percentages, mean and standard deviation. For the 5-point Likert scale questions, the scale and decision rule stated below were employed in analyzing the data.

Scale:

Strongly Agree (SA) -	5
Agree (A)	4
Neutral (N) -	3
Disagree (D) -	2
Strongly Disagree (SD)	1

Decision Rule

If Mean \geq 3.0, the respondents agree

If mean < 3.0, the respondents disagree

Regression Test

Regression analysis was used to test the five hypotheses to determine the nature, and strength of the research variables.

Fomula for regression

$$Y_i = f(X_1 \beta) + e_i$$

X = dependent variable

F = function

X₁ = independent variable

β = coefficient

e_i = error terms

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSES

346 copies of the questionnaire were duly completed and returned representing 91 percent, while 38 copies of the questionnaire were not duly completed and returned from the respondents representing 9 percent. Therefore, a total of 346 (91%) copies was used for analysis.

Tests for Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Destination attraction does not have significant positive influence on satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria.

H_{a1}: Destination attraction have significant positive influence on satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria.

Table 2: ANOVA of the Regression Model

Model	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sign (P-Value)
Regression	32.451	3	5.409	-8.258	0.631
Residual	203.687	343	.655		
Total	236.138	346			

Source: Extracted from SPSS Version 25

Table 3: Estimated Regression of the Model

Model	Coefficient	Std. error	t	Sign
Constant	0.007	0.241	4.4173	0.631
Destination attraction	0.067	0.031	2.169	0.631

Fitness Model of the Variables

Note that the descriptive analysis in table 2 and 3 where combined in testing hypothesis one. The result of the linear regression analysis carried out on the interaction between destination attraction (independent variable) and satisfaction of tourists' needs (dependent variable) is presented in table 2 and 3 above using Fisher's (F) test and probability (P) value as the decision criteria. The Fishers's test value presented in table 3 above with F- value of -8.258 and P value of 0.631 (P>0.05) at 5% level of

significance indicate that destination attraction has no significant positive influence on satisfaction of tourists' needs. Based on this, we reject the alternate hypothesis and accept null which states that destination attraction have no significant positive influence on satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria. The result of the coefficient in table 4.6 shows that a 1% change in destination attraction will decrease 6.7% in tourists' satisfaction.

Test of Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Destination price do not have significant positive influence on satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria.

H₀₂: Destination price have significant positive influence on satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria.

Table 4: ANOVA of the Regression Model

Model	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sign P(Value)
Regression	33.351	3	6.409	-7.158	0.741
Residual	204.787	343	.755		
Total	233.238	346			

Source: Extracted from SPSS Version 25

Table 5: Estimated Regression of the Model

Model	Coefficient	Std. error	t	Sign (P-Value)
Constant	0.147	0.341	3.4173	0.741
Destination prices	0.167	0.231	3.169	0.741

The descriptive analysis in table 4 and 5 where combined in testing hypothesis two. The result of the linear regression analysis carried out on the interaction between destination prices (independent variable) and satisfaction of tourists' needs (dependent variable) is presented in table 4 and 5 above using Fisher's (F) test and probability (P) value as the decision criteria, the Fisher's test value presented in table 4 above with F- value of -7.158 and P value of 0.741 ($P > 0.05$) at 5% level of significance indicate that destination price have no significant positive influence on satisfaction of tourists' needs. Based on this we reject the alternate hypothesis and accept null which states that destination attraction has no significant positive influence on satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria. The result of the coefficient in table 4.6 shows that a 1% negative change in destination attraction will decrease 6.7% in tourists' satisfaction

Summary of Findings

After data analysis, the following findings were made:

- i. Destination attraction had no significant positive influence on satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria (f-sat -8.250, pv 0.631 > 0.05).
- ii. Destination price had no significant positive influence on satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria (f-sat -7.158, pv 0.741 > 0.05).

Conclusion

Based on the findings we concluded that tourism products' dimensions had no significant positive influence on satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria. It was also concluded that tourism product dimensions specifically destination attraction, and destination price were very poor and do not satisfy the needs of in-bound and out-bound tourists' in Nigeria. The qualities of the variables examined were so poor to attract tourist's attention in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Having analyzed, discussed and interpreted the data collected in this study, the author therefore recommends the following:

- i. Sites managers should make the sites very attractive to visitors.
- ii. Sites managers should fix affordable prices for the services rendered to visitors.

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